

D5.2 Report on Expert panel minutes

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COVER PAGE

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Description	The report will include the most important details on the expert panel that will be held at FEUN. It will be focused on analysing the possibilities for further development of the entrepreneurial ecosystem and enhancing innovative processes in the business sector and presenting guidelines for policy makers. The report will include the list of participants and main conclusions.
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VERSIONING AND CONTRIBUTION HISTORY

Version	Date	Change History	Author(s)
1.0	23/04/2025	First version prepared by FEUN	Sandra Milanovic Zbiljic
2.0	24/05/2025	Expert panel minutes	Sandra Milanovic Zbiljic
3.0	25/04/2025	Special session at conference minutes	Marija Radosavljevic
Final	30/04/2025	Final version submitted to the EC	Marija Radosavljevic

DISCLAIMER

This research is part of the 101120390 - USE IPM - HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-03-01 project, funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

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ACRONYMS

Acronym	Full name
EU	European Union
PC	Project Coordinator
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

The Expert panel's main aim was to present to a wider community defined Guidelines for local and government policies. FEUN organized the Expert panel to present Guidelines for policymakers. The panel also explored ways to boost innovation processes within the business sector. It served as a platform to highlight to key authorities, such as Regional Development Agencies (RDAs), Chambers of Commerce (CoCs), and others, the critical need for their support in fostering innovation among businesses.

The event, hosted by FEUN, brought together a diverse group of participants, including representatives from partner organizations, policymakers, business leaders, science and technology parks, development agencies, chambers of commerce, the scientific community, young researchers, and members of the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB).

Therefore, this document sums up all activities conducted during the USE IPM Expert panel held in Niš, Serbia (Table 1).

Table 1: The Expert panel details

Meeting place	Live, Faculty of Economics, Niš, Serbia,		
Meeting date	April 24-25, 2025		
Version	1.0		
Author	Sandra Milanovic Zbiljic		
Type of meeting	Expert panel		
Partners	Attending in person	Marija Radosavljevic (PC)	FEUN
		Sandra Milanovic Zbiljic	FEUN
		Biljana Djordjevic	FEUN
		Aleksandra Andjelkovic	FEUN
		Maja Ivanovic Djukic	FEUN
		Danijela Stosic Panic	FEUN
		Suzana Djukic	FEUN
		Jelena A. Stankovic	FEUN
		Ruzica Petrovic	FEUN
		Jovana Milenovic	FEUN
		Milica Ristic Cakic	FEUN
		Vesna Jankovic Milic	FEUN
		Dejan Djordjevic	FEUN
		Marija Petrovic Randjelovic	FEUN
		Sonja Jovanovic	FEUN
		Ivana Filipovic	FEUN
		Tatjana Stevanovic	FEUN
		Snezana Radukic	FEUN
		Zarko Popovic	FEUN
		Dejan Djordjevic	FEUN
Milan Perkovic	FEUN		
Gorica Boskovic	FEUN		
Ognjen Radovic	FEUN		
Perseta Grabova	UT		

		Elona Pojani	UT
		Ada Bici	UT
		Saša Petkovic	UBL
		Ljubisa Micic	UBL
		Vesna Bucevska	USK
		Stojan Debariev	USK
		Ljubomir Drakulevski	USK
		Donato Iacobucci	UNIVPM
		Hugo Barros	UALg
		Susana Imaginário	UALg
		Fabio Frangipani	Ocom
		Erina Guraziu	Ocom
		Emir Coric	ALDA
		Maja Varoslija	ALDA
		Marko Kolakovic	IIE
		Ivan Turcic	IIE
		Tin Horvatinovic	IIE
		Mladen Turk	IIE
		Panayiotis Kontakos	SAB
	Online	Rosario Pavone	SME4
		Angela Callejon Gill	UMA
		Iain Bitran	ISPIM
		Dragana Radicic	SAB
		Omer Kursad Tufekci	Büyükkutlu Faculty of Applied Sciences, Dean, Turkey
		Ferdi Akbiyik	Isparta University of Applied Sciences, Turkey
Policy makers	In person	Goran Zlatkovic	Regional Development Agency South, RDA, Nis (Serbia)
		Goran Mladenovic	Nis Cluster of Advanced Technologies, NICAT, Nis (Serbia)
		Mina Mitic	Scientific Technology Park Nis, STP Nis (Serbia)
		Zorana Stankovic	Society of Economists Nis, DEN (Serbia)
		Aleksandar Zdraljjevic	The City Administration for Local Economic Development and Investments, KLER, Nis (Serbia)
Report writer	FEUN	Sandra Milanovic Zbiljic	
Report assessor	FEUN	Marija Radosavljevic	

Source: Authors' presentation.

2. LIST OF PARTICIPANTS

The USE IPM Expert panel was in person at the Faculty of Economics premises at April 24, 2025. All partners were invited through their e-mail addresses using formal project e-mail (Figure 1). For all participants accessing the panel online, the Zoom link was created previously. Also, for all partners a formal [invitation](#) from the project coordinator was made and sent to them.

Figure 1: An invitation e-mail for the Expert panel

Figure 2: Photos of the Expert panel participants

Attendance list for [the first](#) and [the second](#) day are linked to this document.

3. AGENDA

For the Expert panel, 2-day [agenda](#) was made. The first day was dedicated to the Expert panel, while the second day was reserved for the dedicated [session](#) for the USE IPM project at the Faculty of Economics *17th International Conference of Strategic Research on Scientific Studies and Education (17th ICoSReSSE)*, organizations: Faculty of Economic University of Niš, Serbia, and Isparta University of Applied Sciences, Türkiye. Agenda's content was previously agreed with project's partners. It should be stressed that conference session is an added value to the expert panel since the expert panel participants had the opportunity to present their research.

4. MEETING SUMMARY AND KEY ISSUES

Date: April 24, 2025

10.00 - 10.30 am

Speakers: Dejan Djordjevic, PhD, vice-dean for scientific research at FEUN, Omer Kursad Tufekci, conference organiser for Turkey, Marija Petrovic Randjelovic, PhD, conference organiser at FEUN, Marija Radosavljevic, PhD, Project Coordinator, FEUN (Serbia) greeted all guests and opened the Expert panel and 17th ICoSReSSE conference. Afterwards, Sandra Milanovic Zbiljic, PhD, FEUN (Serbia) presented key detail for the USE IPM project to familiarize policymakers and conference participants with the main focus and results.

10.45 – 11.00 am

Speaker: Biljana Djordjevic, FEUN (Serbia)

Report: On behalf of the research team of FEUN (Faculty of Economics, University of Nis), Professor Biljana Djordjevic, PhD, presented the key challenges and recommendations to policymakers in Serbia regarding the four areas: soft skills development, sustainability and ESG reporting, technology transfer and open innovation, and innovation process management.

When it comes to soft skills development for successful entrepreneurship, Biljana Djordjevic highlighted key challenges in this area in Serbia, such as the fact that the educational system in Serbia does not adequately support the development of soft skills, the students lack practical experience in acquiring these skills, and some soft skills essential for

business are underestimated. To address these shortcomings, she proposed several measures for policymakers in Serbia, including accrediting modules and courses at universities that focus on developing various soft skills, funding projects dedicated to soft skills development in educational institutions, offering free courses and training for teachers and university professors on methodologies for developing soft skills, encouraging universities to provide short-cycle courses and programmes aimed at improving or developing soft skills, and incentivising companies to offer internships for students to develop certain types of soft skills through tax benefits or other financial incentives.

Regarding sustainability and ESG reporting, Biljana Djordjevic emphasised key challenges in this field, such as the lack of awareness about the importance of sustainability among many companies and individuals in Serbia, the absence of inadequacy of recycling infrastructure in many areas, and the fact that legal obligations for sustainability reporting exist only for large companies. In order to overcome these challenges, she proposed several measures for policymakers, such as providing tax benefits for enterprises that adopt sustainable practices, raising public awareness about the importance of sustainability and proper waste sorting, building appropriate infrastructure for waste collection and recycling at both household and enterprise levels across the country, offering subsidies for companies engaged in waste recycling, expanding the obligation of sustainability reporting to small and medium-sized enterprises as well as other institutions, etc.

Biljana Djordjevic also identified several challenges in the fields of technology transfer and open innovation, and innovation management. She noted that although many actors exist in Serbia's open innovation ecosystem, collaboration among them is sporadic and mostly project-based; there is a gap between state support and the needs of small businesses; there is a necessity for improving intellectual property protection laws in line with EU standards; and there is a lack of sufficient institutional support for sustainable innovation. To overcome these challenges, she proposed several measures for policymakers in Serbia, such as providing incentives for joint research and projects among innovation ecosystem stakeholders, encouraging universities to develop practical, market-driven projects in collaboration with the business sector, strengthening institutional support for green innovations within companies, etc.

In conclusion, Biljana Djordjevic said that by implementing the proposed policies and measures by policymakers, many of the identified challenges could be successfully overcome. However, the dialogue with policymakers and other actors in the open innovation ecosystem regarding the mentioned four areas will continue through further activities within the USE IPM project.

11.00 – 11.15 am

Speaker: Ada Bici, UT (Albania)

Report: During the agenda, Ada Bici, PhD (c), Lecturer at the University of Tirana, presented the research work on behalf of the team. The presentation highlighted key challenges facing Albania and delivered actionable recommendations for policymakers, backed by concrete policy proposals, programs, and measures across four strategic areas (Sustainability, Soft Skills for entrepreneurial business, Technology Sharing and Open innovation, Innovation Process Management) all designed to boost research and development in sustainable entrepreneurship and process innovation management.

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Based on the results of the focus groups were discussed the following recommendations:

1. Albanian businesses can foster a culture of innovation by promoting openness to change and encouraging long-term thinking. Strengthening connections between the education system and SMEs can bridge knowledge gaps, while empowering managers to delegate can free up time for strategic innovation.
2. To drive sustainable development, Albania must implement structured policies, develop ESG frameworks, and encourage businesses to integrate sustainable practices. Raising public awareness and improving waste management systems are crucial for long-term environmental responsibility.
3. Albania must prioritize soft skills training across all levels of education and professional development. Encouraging hands-on learning, mentorship programs, and government-supported initiatives can help bridge the current gap and better prepare the workforce for future demands.

In order to archive the aforementioned results, we are opening the door to an ongoing conversation with policymakers and other key stakeholders in Albania. Our goal is to foster stronger collaboration, and partnerships within the country's evolving entrepreneurial ecosystem. To advance this effort, a roundtable will be organized at the Faculty of Economics, University of Tirana, in autumn 2025. This event will focus on translating the presented recommendations into action and shaping a comprehensive R&I strategy and action plan for Albania.

11.15 – 11.30 am

Speaker: Sasa Petkovic, UBL (Bosnia and Herzegovina)

Report: As part of the agenda, on behalf of the research team of the CPME – Center for Project Management and Entrepreneurship of the University of Banja Luka, UBL project coordinator Sasa Petkovic, PhD, Professor, presented the key challenges and recommendations to policymakers in Bosnia and Herzegovina, along with concrete policy proposals, programs, and measures in four thematic areas, aimed at enhancing research and development in the fields of sustainable entrepreneurship and process innovation management.

Following the presentation and throughout the day, I received feedback and a high level of agreement regarding the proposed recommendations from a large number of participants in the expert panel, including experts from the entrepreneurial ecosystem. I would highlight the following as the most important recommendations:

1. Curricular reform through the introduction of entrepreneurship, innovation, and sustainable development as mandatory subjects and/or as additional complementary learning outcomes and exit competencies across all levels of formal education, along with support for non-formal education initiatives.
2. Support for A2B cooperation (academia-to-business) through subsidies, fiscal incentives, vouchers, the establishment of an innovation fund, grants, and co-financing for SMEs engaged in active fundraising activities through project management towards EU and other funding sources. This support should focus on: digital transformation programs, the introduction and application of project management in process innovation management leading to sustainable entrepreneurship, and the strengthening of soft skills and knowledge for intellectual property protection, knowledge transfer within open innovation systems, and commercialization of sustainable (green and smart) innovations.

3. Raising awareness among a wide range of stakeholders about the necessity of establishing and strengthening the entrepreneurial innovation ecosystem in Bosnia and Herzegovina through the establishment of open innovation systems based on the Quintuple Helix model.

Finally, instead of a formal conclusion, we will continue the dialogue with policymakers, as well as other stakeholders in Bosnia and Herzegovina, towards a more active dialogue, partnership, and cooperation among all key actors of the emerging entrepreneurial ecosystem. This will be pursued through roundtable at the Faculty of Economics of the University of Banja Luka, in the autumn of 2025, where we will discuss the implementation of the above-mentioned recommendations and the adoption of an R&I strategy and action plan in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

11.30 – 11.45 am

Speaker: Stojan Debarliev, USK (North Macedonia)

Report: During the expert panel, Stojan, PhD, Head of the Yunus Social Business Centre, Faculty of Economics – Skopje, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, presented the "Guidelines for Policymakers" developed within the USE IPM project, focusing on strengthening the entrepreneurial ecosystem in North Macedonia. His key insights highlighted the urgent need for systemic reforms in four areas: soft skills development, sustainability and ESG reporting, technology transfer and open innovation, and innovation process management.

He emphasized that bridging gaps between education and practice, especially through interdisciplinary soft skills education and stronger academia-business collaboration, is critical for nurturing entrepreneurial talent. He also stressed the necessity of aligning national policies with EU standards on sustainability, promoting ESG adoption among SMEs, and enhancing digital infrastructure for improved ESG reporting. Regarding technology transfer, he underlined the importance of simplifying IP protection processes, fostering institutional trust, and encouraging market-oriented innovation. Finally, he pointed out that innovation process management must shift toward fast, flexible support mechanisms, particularly for socially responsible and sustainable start-ups. These guidelines aim not only to tackle systemic barriers but also to unlock new opportunities for inclusive, innovation-driven growth in North Macedonia.

Additionally, the insights and recommendations from the Guidelines will be directly utilized in the preparation of the new Strategy for Research and Innovation at the Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, helping to align the University's strategic priorities with national and European trends in entrepreneurship, sustainability, and innovation.

11.45 – 11.50 am

Speaker: Rosario Pavone, SME4SPACE (Belgium), online

Report: We would like to underline the successful experience of bringing Europe together for the Space missions thanks to the primary role of the European Space Agency (ESA). The 50 years of collaboration among European Countries made it possible to achieve great results and innovation in Space, which is a very capital-intensive sector at the edge of technological innovation. No European Country alone could do the same, but together we succeeded. Nowadays we also the European Union, after the Lisbon Treaty, in 2008, has a relevant role mainly in bringing back benefits to citizens from space activities. This is possible thanks to the already established flagship programmes such as Copernicus, Galileo and news ones to come like IRIS2, EU SST. However, apart from those flagship programmes, SME4SPACE has since decade highlighted the importance to foresee small programmes both within ESA and European Union roadmaps where SMEs can have a leading role and allow them to provide end-to-end products and services. Presented Guidelines for policymakers included recommendations for technology transfer that are based on the lessons learned and learning by doing tasks performed during secondments to SME4SPACE. Rosario emphasized the importance of Intellectual property rights and included this topic in the Guidelines, but also as a subject of the training programme that should be created and implemented during the USE IPM project.

Coffee break

12.05 – 12.10 pm

Speaker: Erina Guraziu, PhD, OpenCom (Italy)

Report: Erina delivered a reflection on Educational Approaches to Sustainability and Project Management. Research in educational science shows that soft skills cannot be directly taught but must be acquired through experiential learning, reflective learning, critical reflective learning, and transformational learning. This requires using inquiry as a learning device and recontextualizing learning from business to academia. Active learning methodologies prove effective when case studies originate from real workplaces rather than being invented by professors.

Sustainability requires tools, awareness, and knowledge, but most importantly, it demands a mindset change. This includes developing soft skills related to managing change effectively and embracing change as a structural element of business to maintain competitiveness.

Projects serve as vehicles for introducing change. To ensure this change leads to effective results that produce meaningful value, project management competencies are essential. Therefore, achieving sustainable transformation requires project management skills. Project management can be defined as the discipline through which we transform ideas into impactful value through planning, delegating, monitoring, controlling, and communicating. Projects bring together interdisciplinary competencies where the human element is crucial for success. The project environment becomes a community of practice where people learn from each other—a concept particularly relevant for open innovation.

Indeed, project management is highlighted in the World Economic Forum's Future of Jobs Report 2023 as one of the fastest-growing professions (ranking 26th among 106 analyzed professions) and among the key roles for business transformation across 27 countries.

Learning project management through active learning methodologies and using it as a pedagogical device efficiently helps students acquire the transversal/soft skills that support their sustainability mindset—first as citizens of sustainability, and then as sustainable entrepreneurs capable of producing meaningful impact. We value KPIs as tools to measure success, learn from failure, and promote knowledge management and continuous improvement.

12.10 – 12.15 pm

Speaker: Emir Coric, ALDA, France

Report: As part of the agenda, on behalf of ALDA – European Association for Local Democracy, Emir presented what ALDA does both in Europe and in the region and key challenges along with recommendations to the Guidelines for policymakers aimed at enhancing sustainable entrepreneurship. He introduced ALDA as a non-governmental organization dedicated to promoting good governance and citizen participation at the local level across Europe and beyond. Founded in 1999, ALDA supports local democracy, human rights, and sustainable development by working with local authorities, civil society organizations, and communities. Through a wide range of projects and partnerships, ALDA empowers citizens and fosters collaboration between different stakeholders to build resilient, inclusive societies. For two decades ALDA has been a regional organisation gathering 300 members, active in 54 countries, especially active as a key stakeholder in the field in democracy, democratic and social surroundings. Strong policies begin at the local level. In France, they support cooperation between local democratic organisations.

Following the presentation of the ALDA, Emir highlighted the following as the most important recommendations about the guidelines:

1. Advocacy for Education Reform: CSOs, especially European that have extensive experience in transferring knowledge, should be engaged in advocacy campaigns to integrate soft skills development into formal education curricula and non-formal learning programs.

2. CSO Inclusion in all processes: In the establishment of Community Learning Centres (CLCs), it is essential to prioritize cooperation with Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) that have already developed and implemented programs focused on soft skills development for youth. Partnering with professional and experienced CSOs ensures the integration of proven methodologies and best practices into the CLC framework. Many of these CSOs also bring valuable European expertise, offering insights and approaches aligned with EU standards and practices. Their involvement can significantly enhance the quality and relevance of the learning programs. Furthermore, these CSOs can play a key role in delivering soft skills training in collaboration with local communities, thereby strengthening both local ownership and the overall impact of the CLCs.

3. Creating partnerships with local and regional authorities in all components of the Guidelines.

4. Public-Private Dialogues: ALDA encourages local dialogues between authorities, civil society, and business to co-create policies that reflect grassroots needs.

Representatives of this partner praised the Guidelines and suggested further collaboration with regional decision-makers, towards a more active dialogue, partnership, and cooperation among all key actors of the emerging entrepreneurial ecosystem.

12.15 – 12.20 pm

Speaker: Marko Kolaković, PhD, International Institute of Entrepreneurship (CROATIA)

Report: Marko presented the activities of the IIE as an independent institution with more than 30 active members and more than 1,300 professors, teachers, or doctors from around the world in the field of entrepreneurship. To promote the competence of entrepreneurs, main activities are organising seminars, conferences, and events to bring together entrepreneurs, publish newspapers. Meet the needs of investors, how to invest in Croatia. Their main activities are planning and organizing workshops, seminars, symposia conferences, connecting with companies, investors, and other entrepreneurial associations to promote post-operation entrepreneurship abroad, but also to collect information and to share experiences with other countries.

First, while the guidelines focus on Serbia, Albania, Bosnia & Herzegovina, and North Macedonia, the challenges and solutions are directly applicable to Croatia. Future versions could broaden the scope to include Croatia explicitly. Second, the importance of developing an entrepreneurial mindset should be more strongly emphasized, starting from early education. Formal training is important, but encouraging risk-taking, creativity, and resilience is essential. Third, Croatia's experiences with technology transfer offices, innovation hubs, and proof-of-concept funds could be shared as best practices. Policymakers should also encourage direct collaboration between academia and business through vouchers, competitions, and innovation programs. Fourth, sustainability measures must include practical toolkits and sector-specific guidance, not just general ESG promotion. Stronger collaboration with businesses is key to success. Fifth, the creation of digital platforms to connect entrepreneurs, researchers, and investors has worked well in Croatia and could be vital for Western Balkans integration. Finally, we recommend that future policies define measurable KPIs and monitoring tools to ensure long-term impact and improvement. Overall, the guidelines are timely, realistic, and a solid foundation for boosting entrepreneurial capacity in the region. The International Institute of Entrepreneurship (Croatia) supports this initiative and welcomes opportunities for regional collaboration and knowledge exchange.

12.20 – 12.25 pm

Speaker: Iain Bitran, ISPIM (United Kingdom), online

Report: Iain presented his insights about the secondment to ISPIM in both groups and stressed the importance of cooperation between academic and non-academic sectors in order to bring an entrepreneurial ecosystem in Western Balkan countries. He stressed that partnerships based on the quadruple helix model, between government, academia, industry, and society can stimulate sustainable innovation. This collaboration can be facilitated through public-private partnerships, business incubators, accelerators, and open innovation initiatives.

12.25 – 12.30 pm

Speaker: Donato Iacobucci, PhD, UNIVPM (Italy)

Report: Professor Donato Iacobucci from Marche Polytechnic University discussed their 10-year entrepreneurship education program, emphasizing the importance of incorporating entrepreneurship and transfer of technologies across all subjects rather than treating it as a separate course. He briefly touched three points of entrepreneurship. The meaning of entrepreneurship, second how to implement the program and third is how to connecting education with practice. Entrepreneurship is related to the mindset of person but it is also to develop ideas and put them in practice. So, we have to provide students with creativity, innovation, risk taking, planning, managing projects. He stated that entrepreneurship education needs to be changed in order to support persons for entrepreneurship and offer them programs that all subject have in it, not just on subject. Teachers are key actors in Italy for entrepreneurship. The importance of connection with eco-system, so cooperation is very important (incubators, CoC, clusters etc.). As recommendations for policy members, the programs that involve entrepreneurship education and policy makers are very important. He highlighted their success in receiving a 600,000 euro grant to extend such program.

12.30 – 12.35 pm

Speaker: Hugo Barros, PhD, UAlg (Portugal)

Report: On behalf of the research team of the University of Algarve, namely from its Division of Entrepreneurship and Knowledge Transfer (CRIA), Hugo Barros, coordinator of CRIA, presented the key challenges and recommendations to policymakers in Portugal and in the Algarve region regarding the four areas, namely: soft skills development and entrepreneurship, sustainability and ESG reporting, technology transfer and open innovation, and innovation process management. Hugo Barros started by presenting the University of Algarve, namely the organization of faculties and schools, the actions of the Division of Entrepreneurship and Knowledge Transfer, and the UALG TEC ecosystem of UAlg, focusing on the third mission of the University, the Algarve and Portugal Smart Specialization Strategy, and on its experience outcomes and learnings. Also, it started by mentioning that as a all, Portugal and in particularly the Algarve region, shares most of the challenges identified in the USE IPM report.

When it comes to soft skills development for successful entrepreneurship, Hugo Barros highlighted key challenges in this area in Portugal, such as the lack of focus of the educational system in Portugal regarding the development of soft skills as well as soft skills for entrepreneurs. To address these challenges, actions have been proposed and implemented, such as entrepreneurship programs in high schools, micro accreditation modules and courses at universities, and soft skills curricula in academia,

as well as Lifelong Learning Programs, through the use of EU ESF). Moreover, recommendations have fostered the development of Internship Programs within the Business Sector, bridging a stronger cooperation among academia and companies.

Regarding sustainability and ESG reporting, Hugo Barros emphasized the developments in Portugal, highlighting that this has become a key framework for assessing and managing companies, capitalizing on the Sustainability Report, coordinated by IAPMEI – EU Directive (UE) 2022/2464, and adopted in November 2022, that forces SMEs to report/disseminate information regarding environment, social and human rights. In order to overcome the challenges of sustainability and act accordingly, Portugal and in particular the Algarve region offers a significant number of programs and calls directed to foster sustainability, focused on market lead R+D+I initiatives, namely competitive technologies and scalable solutions (market driven innovation).

Hugo Barros also identified several challenges in the fields of technology transfer and open innovation, and innovation management, drawing attention to the development of the Algarve regional innovation ecosystem, trademarked ALGARVE TECH HUB, and highlighting the existence of a structural regional strategy focused on talent retaining and talent attraction, anchored in national strategy and programs, the existence of a structured Innovation Ecosystem, supported by National, Regional and Local stakeholders, characterized by trust among agents, the emphasis on market lead R+D+I initiatives, and the relevance of clear, realistic, temporal and quantifiable KPI's. Moreover, it was presented that the region, and in a broad cooperation among the regional stakeholders, was able to recognize and identify the most relevant bottlenecks and design specific programs for overcoming them, resulting in a more recognizable and accessible program. Through these actions, the Algarve open innovation ecosystem can foster academia-company collaboration bridging the gap. Also, the existence of a highly relevant IP regulation for researchers at UAlg, promoting knowledge transfer and market based academic research, supported on the capacity to patent and to develop proof of concepts and Minimum Viable Products (MVP), as well as tailored Educational Programs to Support Innovation, based on specific funding programs.

In conclusion, Hugo Barros stated that the implementation of the presented actions, policies and measures, has allowed for the growth of innovation, entrepreneurship, knowledge transfer and sustainability, diversifying the regional economy and improving its competitiveness index.

12.35 – 12.40 pm

Speaker: Angela Callejon Gil, PhD, UMA (Spain)

Report: Angela had technical difficulties to connect to the meeting. Therefore, she delivered her insights in text form. The objective of this project is to promote research and development in the fields of sustainable entrepreneurship and process innovation. To that aim, this abstract has been prepared by the University of Malaga (UMA) team, to summarise the content of our work, which is organised into the areas that make up the USE-IPM Guideline for Policy Makers: (1) Soft skills for Entrepreneurial Business, (2) Sustainability and Sustainability Reports, (3) The transfer of technology and the concept of open innovation. Innovation.

1. Soft skills for Entrepreneurial Business. The introduction of educational models in Spain that incorporate the development of soft skills is imperative, ensuring that students receive comprehensive training and are able to adapt to business demands. In order to achieve this, it is essential that universities recognise the importance of complementing their studies with this training, and that businesses and entrepreneurs become more involved at the university level. To this aim, it is necessary to explore the notion of establishing a stronger connection between the academic and business worlds.

2. Sustainability and Sustainability Reports. Spanish companies are confronted with the challenge of sustainability and the significant requirements; as such, there is a necessity for sustainability professionals who can provide technical solutions and are capable of preparing the necessary reports. It is the responsibility of the university to ensure that its students are adequately prepared to meet the business sector's demands. It is imperative that a business culture is established which accords due importance to the necessity of responsible and sustainable behaviour.

3. Technology transfer and the concept of open innovation. Innovation management represents a further significant challenge at both university and business levels, particularly for SMEs, as this adaptation necessitates a considerable investment of effort. It is anticipated that well-qualified university students will be the young professionals best placed to incorporate these new processes into businesses. Technological innovation is understood to originate in academic institutions, such as universities, which are tasked with providing the requisite resources and technologies to facilitate the development and contribution to the business sector.

Research into sustainable entrepreneurial intentions is an imperative component of academic enquiry.

12.40 – 13.00 pm

Comments and suggestions of entrepreneurial eco-system stakeholders

Speakers:

Mina Mitic, Scientific Technology Park Nis, STP Nis (Serbia)

Aleksandar Zdraljevic, The City Administration for Local Economic Development and Investments, KLER, Nis (Serbia)

Zorana Stankovic, Society of Economists Nis, DEN (Serbia)

Goran Mladenovic, Nis Cluster of Advanced Technologies, NICAT, Nis (Serbia)

Goran Zlatkovic, Regional Development Agency South, RDA, Nis (Serbia)

Report: Stakeholders of the entrepreneurial ecosystem emphasized the urgent need to strengthen collaboration between academia, businesses, and public institutions to foster innovation and sustainable entrepreneurship. They pointed out that despite having strong policies, their implementation remains weak, particularly in supporting start-ups, technology transfer, and ESG adoption. Challenges such as the lack of financial incentives for circular economy practices, insufficient infrastructure for recycling, slow digital transformation, and the limited integration of sustainable development goals into education were highlighted. Stakeholders also suggested establishing clear and measurable impact indicators, enhancing lifelong learning opportunities, and building stronger regional networks to exchange best practices and ensure the competitiveness of entrepreneurs at both local and European levels.

The event served as an important platform for exchanging ideas and fostering entrepreneurship, with a strong emphasis on connecting local institutions and entrepreneurs. Activities covered are aimed at strengthening competitiveness, promote employment, and enhance territorial development. Particular focus was placed on working with youth, improving education, and deepening cooperation to encourage innovative thinking and entrepreneurial spirit.

While several projects have been successfully implemented through cooperation with the European Union, challenges remain. Innovation is not yet fully embedded across all components of the business sector, and cooperation among new entrepreneurs is still limited. Mentorship emerged as a critical element to strengthen systematic support for young entrepreneurs. Practical solutions identified include integrating entrepreneurship support into existing programs, developing mentorship structures, and creating systems to match young entrepreneurs with researchers to foster innovation.

Regional development agencies were highlighted as key partners, maintaining ongoing cooperation with faculties, including the exchange of lectures and ideas. Strengthening ties between academia and business was recognized as essential for upgrading the entrepreneurial ecosystem, calling for an integral policy approach to improve the supply side of knowledge, soft skills, and an open innovation mindset.

A holistic approach was emphasized, including the transition toward a five-helix model that integrates business, academia, government, civil society, and the environment. The implementation of start-up academies was noted as a key initiative, focusing on building trust between business and technology sectors, upskilling entrepreneurs, and fostering collaboration to create a stronger future for regional entrepreneurship.

Speaker: Panayiotis Kontakos, PhD, Deputy Head of School of Business and Management, Assistant Professor in International Business UCLan, Cyprus (SAB member)

Report: The event served as a celebration of cooperation, demonstrating that beyond their immediate policy relevance, the project outcomes can be translated into valuable, practical tools and frameworks that directly strengthen the entrepreneurial ecosystem. This cooperation showcases how research findings, collaborative initiatives, and strategic dialogues can move beyond theoretical recommendations to generate real-world impact, fostering innovation, building skills, and supporting the sustainable growth of local and regional economies.

13.00 – 13.30 pm

Brainstorming session of all partners and general conclusion of the expert panel

During the brainstorming session, participants discussed the possibilities for developing new forms of cooperation, as well as engaging in the preparation of new project applications that would build upon the results of the USE IPM project. These future initiatives would not only rely on the achievements already made but would also address newly identified challenges faced by the widening countries. In addition, they would incorporate the valuable suggestions and insights provided by partners from across Europe, ensuring broader relevance and a stronger impact on future activities.

Date: April 25, 2025

Conference link: <https://www.mekinacademy.com.tr/ICoSReSSE/>

On the second day of the conference, within the 17th International Conference of Strategic Research on Scientific Studies and Education (ICoSReSSE), a series of research papers were presented focusing on digital transformation and sustainable development. Topics included the analysis of digital nomads in Croatia, the impact of AI tools on linguistic skills development, taxation challenges in the EU digital economy, and the influence of digitalization on environmental quality in the Western Balkans. Presentations also explored the role of digital workplace transformation for organizational sustainability, drivers and challenges of implementing sustainability and circular economy practices, the application of IT tools in business excellence, and the contribution of digital transformation to sustainable regional development. Other discussions covered servitization strategies, the importance of digital transformation for ESG reporting, urban trees diversity for city resilience, and the challenges and opportunities faced by market-oriented companies in Serbia. The session highlighted the critical link between digital innovation, environmental responsibility, and sustainable business practices. Some researchers from the USE IPM project participated at the conference and presented their research. This is value added activity, and not previously planned during the project proposal writing.

5. MANAGEMENT DISCUSSION

Since almost all partners' national team leaders were present at the Expert panel, there was also management discussion during the panel.

The non-academic partners were interested in what obligations they have in continuing the implementation of the project, because the specific activities in which they participated are completed. PC explained that their contribution is expected in the framework of WP4, when they should visit all 4 widening countries to participate in the implementation of the training program. Also, pc emphasized that all partners will be informed about the other activities (writing papers and attending workshops), so that they could even join these activities although they are not provided for in the specific non-academic partner's budget.

It was agreed with the coordinators of the widening partners how the work on developing the R&I strategy will be organized, that it should be focused on the work of the Center for Innovation and Entrepreneurship, and adopted at the level of all 4 faculties of which it will represent. The framework structure of the strategies and accompanying action plans, as well as the template for their preparation, has been defined.

6. RISK MANAGEMENT

In order to mitigate risk of the partner not being able to attend the Expert panel, they attended it online. For partners that had unused travel funds, they can be used for continuing project meetings in order to improve the quality of project implementation and consider continuation of collaboration, for additional dissemination, or can be redirected to other partners whose costs from the same categories exceed the planned amount.

7. PUBLICATION AND DISSEMINATION

The expert panel was previously disseminated using the social network channels for the USE IPM project.

It was announced by one [poster](#) made for this purpose. Also, a [computer background](#) for the Expert panel was made.

Figure 3: Facebook Expert panel announcement

Figure 4: Instagram Expert panel announcement

Figure 5: LinkedIn Expert panel announcement

Moreover, participating partners made post on their social media channels to disseminate their involvement in this project.

Links:

- <https://www.cria.pt/noticias/ualg-cria-integra-painel-de-peritos-na-servia-no-ambito-do-projeto-use-ipm/>
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/pdkontakos_strengthening-sustainable-entrepreneurship-activity-7322665168306393090-UCmz?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACr9nZsB61XAd5eF Xtjl-osBBzBtJKv29ww
- <https://news.opencom-italy.org/opencom/2025/project-management-and-sustainability-a-sinergy-for-the-future-of-education/>

- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/opencom-issc_opencom-useipm-sustainability-activity-7321161620380872704-2_zO?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACr9nZsB61XAd5eFXtjl-osBBzBtJKv29ww
- https://www.instagram.com/p/DI1LBMUKGEJ/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==
- <https://www.facebook.com/cpme.ef.unibl.org/posts/1276347561163528>
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ada-bici-0818a942_useipm-policyworkshop-sustainableinnovation-activity-7321123439354753024-exjx?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACr9nZsB61XAd5eFXtjl-osBBzBtJKv29ww
- <https://cpme.ef.unibl.org/vijesti/use-ipm-clanovi-projektnog-tima-aktivni-na-medjunarodnoj-konferenciji-icosresse-kreiranje-buducnosti-prihvatanje-digitalne-transformacije/>
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/efuniblcpme_useipm-digitaltransformation-organizational sustainability-activity-7322567814081310721-Kp9l?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACr9nZsB61XAd5eFXtjl-osBBzBtJKv29ww
- <https://www.facebook.com/cpme.ef.unibl.org/posts/1279582344173383>
- https://www.instagram.com/p/DI_X-XmoZL8/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/sandra-milanovi%C4%87-zbilji%C4%87-1b7672181_useipm-horizoneurope-activity-7322928441127792640-POut?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACr9nZsB61XAd5eFXtjl-osBBzBtJKv29ww

REFERENCES

- Grant Agreement-Project 101120390-USE IPM (2023).
- Consortium Agreement – USE IPM project (2023).

ANNEX

Reviews of the D5.2 Report on Expert panel minutes

Review 1	
Reviewer Name:	Panayiotis Kontakos, PhD, Deputy Head of School of Business and Management, Assistant Professor in International Business, UCLan, Cyprus, SAB member
Date of review:	29/04/2025
Reviewer opinion: (150 words)	The deliverable “Report on Expert Panel Minutes” is fully aligned with the objectives outlined in Grant Agreement No. 101120390. No further revisions are required by the author or other partners of the USE IPM consortium. General opinion: Accepted; Comments: None.
Review 2	
Reviewer Name:	Marija Radosavljevic, PhD, PC, FEUN
Date of review:	29/04/2025
Reviewer opinion: (150 words)	The deliverable named “Report on expert panel minutes” is in line with the Grant Agreement for project No. 101120390. This document will serve as a strong anchor through the USE IPM project. Therefore, the quality of this deliverable is acceptable to be further processed to the European Union through the SyGMa platform. There is no need for further improvements of the deliverable by the writer and other partners of the USE IPM consortium. General opinion: Accepted; Comments: None.